

**POLITICAL PRESTIGE OF REPUBLIC UZBEKISTAN IN CENTRAL ASIA
REGION**

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Ergashev Islomjon Zuhridin oqli

*Tashkent State University of Oriental Studies
3-course student of faculty " World politics "*

Annotation. *This article covers important priorities of Uzbekistan's foreign policy, the role of Uzbekistan in the world community, its interaction with international organizations, strengthening the international authority of the Republic of Uzbekistan, providing the world community with information on the reforms carried out in the country, improving the regulatory and legal framework of Uzbekistan's foreign policy and foreign economic activity, as well as the*

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As at all times, at the present stage, the foreign policy of the States is being developed and implemented in accordance with the changes taking place in the life of the country and in the international arena. The foreign policy of the states can have positive or negative consequences in international relations. The reason is diverse and we can explain this in the following cases. First of all, some countries try to participate and influence in this relationship, not taking into account their foreign policy, the changes that are taking place in international relations in the development and implementation. Secondly, the foreign policy of states in the regulation of international relations it is important. With the help of foreign policy, states express their attitude to the situation taking place in the international arena and contribute to the solution of the problems arising from it to this or that level.

One of the main and first-level tasks of foreign political activity is the effective implementation of the strategy of action on the five priority directions of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021. In order to achieve this goal, the following tasks are set before the foreign policy office:

- formation of as favorable foreign political conditions as possible for the effective implementation of democratic reforms carried out in our country, as well as the intensive processes of modernization of society and economy;
- Maintaining and strengthening peace and stability in Central Asia, turning the region into a region of security and sustainable development;
- formation of a balanced, multifaceted system of strategic cooperation with the world's leading countries and international organizations;

- It is an indicator of the promotion of international initiatives of Uzbekistan in important areas of regional and world politics.

Uzbekistan has developed cooperation with the United States and countries in Southeast Asia, including Malaysia, Indonesia, Singapore, Vietnam, in order to support the modernization process and reforms aimed at strengthening the foundations of civil society in our country and improving the standard of living of the people. Trade of Uzbekistan with South Asian countries, in particular India and Pakistan, it supports the development of comprehensive and mutually beneficial cooperation in such areas as transport, communications, tourism. Uzbekistan is interested in actively developing and strengthening mutually beneficial relations with the countries of the Muslim world in the fields of economy, transport communications, finance, investment and tourism, including within the framework of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation and the Islamic Development Bank. Uzbekistan will continue to take an active part in the work of the UN, as well as to ensure international peace and security, in the process of rapid globalisation, it sees States as the only non-governmental organization responsible for promoting sustainable development. With the Organization of security and cooperation in Europe, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization and the Commonwealth of Independent States, our country is committed to further developing cooperation with the aim of effectively using these structures to combat modern problems and threats, developing multilateral cooperation.

Uzbekistan cooperates with them as a member of specialized institutions within the framework of the UN - the World Health Organization, the International Labour Organization, the World Intellectual Property Organization, the International Children's fund (UNICEF), the International Postal Union, the International Union for electrical communication, the World Meteorological Organization, the International Olympiad, the International Automobile Union and other organizations. International financial and economic organizations for the implementation of economic reforms in Uzbekistan, its integration with the world community - The International Monetary Fund, the World Bank, the International Financial Corporation, the European bank for reconstruction and development are also contributing. International Trade Center (YuNKTAD), is cooperating with.

Uzbekistan, as an independent state, has joined the Vienna Convention on the protection of the ozone layer of the planet, the Montreal Protocol on substances that reduce the ozone layer, the Convention on the Prohibition of the military or other hostile use of means that affect the environment, the Treaty on the non-proliferation of nuclear weapons.

Thus, Uzbekistan has historically joined the world community in a short period of time, has risen to the level of a prestigious state that is actively involved in solving international and regional problems, strengthening general and regional security.

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